

USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Mirzarakhimova Aziza Bakhrom qizi¹, Rustamova Ziyoda²

^{1,2}Assistant at Tashkent State University of Economics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15289210>

Аннотация. В данной научной работе анализируется содержание и система интерактивных технологий в инновационной образовательной среде, обосновываются компоненты интерактивной технологии, раскрывается основная педагогическая идея и основные требования в режиме интерактивной технологии для успешного обучения. Сгруппированы и проанализированы виды активных методов в режиме интерактивной технологии для успешного обучения и стимулирования естественной активности студентов. Показаны способы создания инновационной образовательной среды в высшем учебном заведении в режиме интерактивной технологии.

Ключевые слова: Интерактивные технологии, образовательная система, инновационное образование, интерактивные методы обучения, инновационная деятельность.

Abstract. This scientific work analyzes the content and system of interactive technologies in an innovative educational environment, substantiates the components of interactive technology, reveals the main pedagogical idea and the main requirements in the interactive technology mode for successful learning. The types of active methods in the interactive technology mode for successful learning and stimulation of natural activity of students are grouped and analyzed. The ways of creating an innovative educational environment in a higher educational institution in the interactive technology mode are shown.

Key words: Interactive technologies, educational system, innovative education, interactive teaching methods, innovative activities.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu ilmiy ishda innovatsion ta'lim muhitida interfaol texnologiyalarning mazmuni va tizimi tahlil qilingan, interfaol texnologiyaning tarkibiy qismlari asoslab berilgan, asosiy pedagogik g'oya va interaktiv texnologiya rejimida muvaffaqiyatli ta'lim olish uchun asosiy talablar ochib berilgan. Muvaffaqiyatli o'rganish va o'quvchilarning tabiiy faolligini rag'batlantirish uchun interfaol texnologiya rejimida faol usullarning turlari guruhlangan va tahlil qilingan. Interfaol texnologiya rejimida oliy ta'lim muassasasida innovatsion ta'lim muhitini yaratish yo'llari ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: interaktiv texnologiyalar, ta'lim tizimi, innovatsion ta'lim, interaktiv ta'lim Metodi, innovatsion faoliyat.

Interactive technologies make the educational process more interesting and active, based on the personal expression of education seekers and teachers and their active interaction. This allows shifting the emphasis on the development of innovative activities of education seekers and their way of thinking from simple assimilation of information. The leading idea of modern training of creative and innovative individuals is to promote the development of natural talents, qualities, success and intellectual capabilities and the formation of intellectual potential.

Tuning in to further active, creatively conscious self-activity, satisfying their desire to demonstrate personal qualities, self-realization, and meeting the spiritual needs of a person. This

creates an effective method for examining and developing the creative abilities of the student and the comprehensive development of the individual, which is only possible when constructing a subject-subject model of learning in the educational process, where the main importance is given to the use of interactive teaching methods.

Innovative pedagogical activity creates new norms of individually directed, personal and creative activity of the teacher, associated with the rejection of educational stereotypes, and develops pedagogical interactive technologies that are implemented in innovative educational activity. At present, this is becoming especially important, since the priority of the state policy of society is the optimization of professional training with an emphasis on the result, not on the assessment of the learning process, not on the duration of training, but on its quality.

The variety of innovative technologies includes interactive technologies, which involve the interaction of all participants in the educational process, which is carried out using methods that activate pedagogical communication as equal active intersubjective interaction. Interactive technologies help to activate independent creative and research work, which contributes to the development of creative abilities and cognitive activity of students [1].

The development of interactive technologies in an innovative educational environment is currently a pressing issue of the theory and methodology of teaching in the educational process. Based on this, the article examines the following issues:

- 1) Content and system of interactive technologies in an innovative educational environment;
- 2) Components of interactive technology, the main pedagogical idea and the main requirements in the interactive technology mode for successful learning;
- 3) Types of active methods in the interactive technology mode for successful learning;
- 4) Using interactions in interactive technology mode for successful learning and stimulating the natural activity of students;
- 5) Creating an innovative educational environment of the university using interactive technologies;
- 6) Improving the quality of the educational process of the university in interactive technology mode;
- 7) Stages of development of interactive learning technology in the innovative educational environment of the university.
- 8) The impact of the active implementation of information and communication technologies, modern digital tools and new technological teaching aids on the possibilities of using interactive technologies in an innovative educational environment.

The study of the current state of the organization of the educational process indicates the existence of contradictions that require effective solutions, in particular, between:

- The need of modern society for the growth of creative potential, a person capable of creative thinking in non-standard situations, and the insufficient development of practical mechanisms that influence the formation of creative skills;
- Theoretical knowledge acquired and the inability to apply it in practical activities, various life situations, and to creatively analyze a problem;
- The need for interpersonal interaction of students, development of social skills of creative interaction, and a traditionally organized educational space;

– The importance of using interactive technologies in the educational process, insufficient definition of their place in the system of other forms, methods and means, their role in achieving the goal of education [2].

The introduction of interactive technologies into the innovative space of higher education forms the innovative position of a specialist and promotes the readiness of future specialists for innovative activities throughout their lives.

Active learning is interactive because it allows you to teach your participants in collaboration. Each participant's experience, knowledge, and learning process are extremely valuable in this case.

Active learning is interactive because it allows you to teach your participants in collaboration. Each participant's experience, knowledge, and learning process are extremely valuable in this case.

The value for the teacher is that interactive learning allows him to use classroom time rationally and, at the same time, allows the student of a higher education institution to express himself in the educational process and in the course of independent work. Therefore, the use of modern interactive learning technologies - educational technologies in classes at a university will make classes innovative and meaningful, and at the same time, the teacher will easily involve students in the learning process.

The main pedagogical idea of using interactive technologies in an innovative educational environment is to update basic knowledge, activate the thinking activity of university students, provide the opportunity for independent understanding of the meaning for the practical use of acquired knowledge, foster a positive attitude towards the subject, and individualize the educational process [3].

Interactive learning technologies in an innovative educational environment provide for the organization of cooperative learning, when each member of the group makes a unique contribution to common achievements, which turn into group individual tasks; the efforts of each member of the group are necessary for the success of the entire group. The skillful use of interactive technologies in an innovative educational environment allows changing the forms of habitual activity, relieving nervous tension, and focusing on the main problems that require priority attention.

Let's consider the basic requirements in the interactive technology mode for successful student learning at a university:

- 1) Group members being in close contact with each other - direct interaction;
- 2) Understanding by group members that this is a joint educational activity that benefits everyone - positive relationships;
- 3) Higher education students learn interpersonal skills that are important for successful and interesting work, such as planning and distributing tasks – developing teamwork skills;

Types of active methods in interactive technology mode for successful learning.

Introductory methods. Introductory methods in interactive technology mode allow to create an atmosphere of trust and goodwill for successful learning. A preliminary meeting is held in the introductory part with the trainer, tasks and purpose of the training, the participants of the training are introduced in interactive technology mode for successful learning, the rules of the training and a survey of their expectations.

Key methods are those that offer a solution to the main problem of the training or lesson. These can be interactive lectures, discussions, role-playing games, brainstorming, carousel, cases, etc. It is important to alternate different types of key methods during the main part of the

training or lesson - for successful learning, for each subsequent stage of work, select a new method in the interactive technology mode that corresponds to the task. Among the key methods, it is worth highlighting the rights to problematization. Their goal is to emphasize the ambiguity and actualize the participants' experience regarding this problem, the relevance of the solution, the complexity of the problem in order to increase the cognitive interest in the topic raised. Part of the problematization function is solved by parallel recording on a flip chart and collecting expectations from training participants in the interactive technology mode. These can also be experiments, business games or cases that highlight the problem and “expose” it [4].

Final methods combine the results into a common structure, summarize the lesson in interactive technology mode, and help to highlight the main results of interactive work for successful learning.

Innovative renewal of the educational system in the interactive technology mode ensures the growth of personal potential, since the university teachers and students contribute to the manifestation of individuality and self-improvement. In interactive technology mode, a teacher must be proficient in teaching methods, know his subject, be oriented in modern socio-political life, and have knowledge in related scientific fields. Taking into account the specifics of educational activities, the specifics of the system of professional training of competitive specialists, the content of training teachers for innovative pedagogical activities, the specifics of the formation of a teacher as a subject of innovative activities, the creation of an innovative educational environment of the university for the successful learning of students and stimulation of their natural activity. Such an educational environment of higher education should be based on the formation of the image of “I am a future competitive specialist”, on the assimilation of innovative professional activity of the individual, on the knowledge of oneself as an individual, the abilities of the individual in professional activity, understanding the intellectual and spiritual foundations of success.

Innovative learning in interactive technology mode helps develop the ability to independently analyze and evaluate information, a more conscious and much deeper understanding of the essence of what is being studied, to argue one's point of view, formulate conclusions, respect alternative opinions, listen to others, build constructive relationships with its members and determine one's place in the team, work in a team. This allows all participants in the educational process to implement the idea of cooperation, helps to ensure an atmosphere of psychological comfort, teaches them constructive interaction. The organization of such training in the interactive technology mode involves the systematic use of specific technologies, methods that implement successful training, and stimulating the natural activity of students with the help of these approaches.

The scientific work shows the importance of using interactive technologies in an innovative educational environment. Research and experimental work has shown that the leading role in the implementation of innovations aimed at the formation of a creative personality and the development of its individuality is performed by a teacher at the level of an educational institution, under whose guidance it is necessary to carry out the process of innovative training of specialists to solve the ways of using interactive technologies in an innovative modern professional environment.

The prospects for further research include studying such issues as the study and implementation of foreign experience in the use of modern interactive teaching technologies.

REFERENCES

1. Balalaieva, O., Mochan, T., Hryhorenko, T., Andreikova, I., Paltseva, V., & Podkovyroff, N. (2023). Innovative pedagogical technologies – the most important resource in modernizing the training of a modern specialist. *Amazonia Investiga*, 12(63), 67-76. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2023.63.03.6>
2. Budnyk, O., Rembierz, M., Arbeláez-Encarnación, T. F., Rojas-Bahamón, M. J., Arbeláez-Campillo, D. F., Chinchoy, A., & Matveieva, N. (2022). Formation of tolerance in the inclusive environment of an educational institution. *Amazonia Investiga*, 11(56), 305-319. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2022.56.08.29>
3. Drozich, I., Drobin, A., Skrypka, I., Mamchych, O., Mykhailenko, O., & Kurach, M. (2023). The role of education the innovative society. *Amazonia Investiga*, 12(64), 45-56. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2023.64.04.4>
4. Knysh, I., Budanova, O., Vakulenko, S., Syrotina, O., & Popychenko, S. (2023). Innovative educational technologies as a way of higher education enhancement. *Amazonia Investiga*, 12(68), 21-32. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2023.68.08.2>
5. Kovalenko, V. V., Marienko, M. V., & Sukhikh, A. S. (2021). Use of augmented and virtual reality tools in a general secondary education institution in the context of blended learning. *Information Technologies and Learning Tools*, 86(6), 70-86. <https://doi.org/10.33407/itlt.v86i6.4664>